

Covid Relief Work of SEWD, Maharashtra during Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

The Covid-19 lockdown provided various opportunities for civil society groups, NGOs, Gov organisation and other agencies to work for welfare of affected individuals, families, communities and society at Large. There are many such role model agencies those extended their help and assistance to those, who were in need of help and assistance. It could be done through direct community engagements, participation or with collaboration. In such a scenario SEWD which is a registered organisation decided to step forward to extend direct relief to people in need during Covid-19. The paper is presenting a case of SEWD.

Key words: Covid-19, Human Rights, Underprivileged, Covid Relief Work.

Introduction

In developing nations, with the lockdown, the underprivileged households face intense deprivation of nutrition and general protection. The extended period of stress could have a drawn out negative effect on their turn of events. During the hour of lockdown, an expanding number of helpless families had no source of daily income, which lead to disappointment, and feelings of vulnerability.

Therefore, SWED organization tried to do help those in need through our Covid Relief Work so that we can ease the difficulties faced by these vulnerable sections of the society. We carried out a baseline survey in the Marathwada region to understand the intensity of the impact caused by the lockdown and to identify the vulnerable families who were in dire need of the basics of life.

SEWD stands for "Society for Equity with Dignity" It is a Non-profit Organization registered under Society Registration Act 1860 & Bombay public trust Act 1950. The SEWD is an initiative of social work professionals from Marathwada region of Maharashtra. The members of this organization represents from different communities and they dreamed the vision that each individual should get an equal opportunity to strive their life with full of dignity. Taking this philosophy further, the organization is formally registered in year of 2010 at Latur, Maharashtra. Majority of its members belongs to social work discipline and they have completed their social work degree from premier institute like TISS, Pune and Solapur University. SEWD came into existence because of several significant reasons. The Marathawada is one of the largest region and which equally consider as one of the most backward region of Maharashtra because of drought prone situation, agrarian crisis, high ratio of unemployment, low sex ration, low literacy, caste discrimination and atrocities against Dalits, women and NT/DNT Communities, huge migration of youths and families in big metropolitan cities like Pune and Mumbai. At another side many marginalized constituencies such Dalit, NT/DNT Communities, women, urban poor (Slum dwellers) are being faced different types discrimination and perhaps continuous atrocity cases happenings in the region.

While looking and facing this blurred situation on day to day basis, the committed groups of young professionals decided to confront these challenges and create an enabling environment for each family to live their life with dignity. It has also been decided that Equality, Justice and Fraternity would be the guiding principles to work upon these challenges. The organization is also striving to promote peace and protection of basic human rights of each and every human being.

VISION of SEWD

A Reconstruction of Society, Based on the Principles of Dignity, Responsible citizenship with rights and duties framework.

MISSION of SEWD

Fight For Right And Commitment For Practicing Duties While Engaging Citizens Into Civic Activities.

GOALS of SEWD

1. To work for the upliftment of underprivileged communities such as Dalit, Adivasi, slum dwellers, women, unorganized workers, children, youths.
2. To work on quality education aspect where child from weaker sections communities would able to access it.
3. To work on unemployment issue through providing skill based training for unemployed youths.
4. To work with different partner agencies to ensure the rights of weaker section in the field of legal justice, education, health and livelihood.
5. To build capacity of different community groups through capacity building training,
6. Providing counselling services to family, youths, adolescents, married couples, and old age people.

Save the Lives during Pandemic

Society for Equity with Dignity (SEWD) is a Non-Governmental Organization working since 2010 in Marathwada region in sector. Organization closely works with poor, marginalized families in the field of education, health and livelihood & counselling. There are multiple vulnerabilities aroused in the present Covid-19 pandemic.

Many poor families are struggling for the basic needs. the organization has launched “Save the Lives” Campaign in Latur District, Marathwada. Last year also many lives were saved through preventive level awareness cum relief work measures. In this 30-days targeted campaign. Organization has planned to reach out in 100 villages for awareness cum relief related work. As of now organization has mobilized following items through different individual donors, foundations, CSR and CSOs.

Covid -19 Relief Work

The Corona Virus Disease (Covid 19) accounted its first instance in India on January 30, 2020. Going by the circumstances in China and some significant nations like USA, Italy and France, the Indian Government had made the prudent stride of declaring the curfew in time and afterwards declaring a lockdown respectively until May 17, 2020 from where began the first phase of lockdown. Each resident of the nation was advised to remain inside the house and step out just in case of emergency while keeping up with the social distancing norms.

The flare-up of COVID-19 carried social and financial life to a halt. The emergency saw a shocking mass departure of such floating populace of migrant workers by walking, in the midst of countrywide lockdown. Their concerns principally were loss of work, ration issues, and nonattendance of a federal retirement aide net.

The rural India, when thought about a place of refuge, has likewise been hit hard, indicating a slow recovery rate. The unemployment rate in the rural regions was 53 percent that was 1.5 times that in the metropolitan regions, which was 36 percent. The work retention rate in metropolitan zones was low and in rural zones, the unemployment rate kept on indicating a rising pattern. This suggested that the quality jobs in metropolitan regions had vanished and there was underemployment in the rural zones.

Issues were additionally raised about whether this sort of reverse migration was because of distress or opportunity related. It is assessed that in excess of 50% migrating laborers would prefer not to return to their own area. Given the nature just as the mutual encounters, the supposed source areas have low social and economic formative records with small possibilities of creating fair job positions.

Enormous migration instigated by more noteworthy and greener fields of financial development is largely a fantasy, as the greater part of the movement is for resource and endurance and falls under the citatory of distress migration. Along with this comes the important part where in due to the stress peoples mental health is getting highly affected.

SWED provided Grocery Kits, which contained oil, wheat, rice etc. to over 250 households from 6 different villages (Budhoda, Salu, Peth being some of the village that we catered to).

Table 1: Division of households

Widow Women	Elderly Persons (60+)	(BPL) Households
50 Households	100 Households	45 Households

Out of 250 households, we catered to 50 households, which had widow women since struggle for them to get food was very difficult. 100 households had elderly people who had no one to look after and therefore, were struggling to get a daily meal.

Out of 100, 45 households were of BPL category with meager to no income and were struggling hard to make ends meet.

Glimpse of Covid-19 Prevention and Relief Activity of SEWD

Conclusion

While looking and facing this blurred situation on day to day basis, the committed groups of young professionals decided to to ease out their concerns of daily ration by providing them with Grocery kits so that they can meet their daily dietary needs and can also ease out their stress thereby, maintain a healthy physical and mental well-being. Though its difficult to confront these challenges and create an enabling environment for each family to live their life with dignity but organization is not compromising on its foundational values and continuously striving to promote peace and protection of basic human rights of each and every human being.

